

PEDAGOGICAL INITIATIVE OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS A PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT MECHANISM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the mechanisms of pedagogical initiative development in future teachers, the possibility of supporting initiatives, the nature of professional initiative, the conditions for its implementation, approaches to pedagogical initiative, and the psychological foundations of pedagogical initiative. This article serves as a resource for the scientific-pedagogical community, students, teachers and researchers.*

Keywords: *pedagogical initiative, educational initiative, renewal, implementation, competence, diagnostic methods, self-development, implementation of one's activity, pedagogical education, pedagogical process, activity, activation.*

The development of the educational system of Uzbekistan shows that the effective implementation of innovative forms, methods, and tools in the educational process depends in most cases on the initiative of the teacher. It is necessary to prepare future teachers for this activity in order to develop them comprehensively on the basis of providing wide-scale pedagogical support to students. Because in this process special demands are placed on the teacher's professional skills. That is why there is a special interest among the scientific and pedagogical community in relation to the concept of professional initiative. In various scientific sources, the concept of professional initiative is interpreted pedagogically. First of all, initiative serves as a resource and a mechanism for personal and professional development of a future teacher. According to L.V. Yablokova, the teacher's professional initiative is not only the introduction of new ideas to the educational process, but also the activity of choosing the educational process, its structure and content in the nature of regularity, flexibility, speed. Because the professional initiative of the teacher is primarily aimed at changing the pedagogical practice. This includes the development of the educational environment and its components on the basis of initiative. The components of the educational process, its goals, content, results, technology, organizational conditions, and principles are improved based on an innovative approach.

The teacher's initiative is understood as the implementation of new forms and forms of activity with a subjective and objective approach. This activity has its external and internal determinants. Indicators of professional initiative of future teachers appear as a way of self-expression and actualization of their activity. Accordingly, within the framework of the concept of professional initiative, the description of the teacher's personal qualities, the method of realizing his creative needs, his professionally significant activity, his aspirations to change a certain part of the pedagogical system, educational goals, laws, content, methods, technologies, and activities related to improving interpersonal relations are understood.

Future teachers strive to master active forms and innovative methods of organizing and implementing the educational process based on educational initiative in the process of professional formation. Professional initiative is a phenomenon that ensures the personal development of a future teacher. On the basis of initiative, future teachers acquire the experience of creative activity that is relevant for them. The issue of developing pedagogical initiative of future teachers should

be widely researched as one of the leading problems of higher pedagogical education. On the one hand, this issue is related to the development of the content of higher pedagogical education, and on the other hand, it is a pedagogical phenomenon that requires the professional and personal development of the future pedagogue. The concept of pedagogical initiative has been introduced into pedagogical use in connection with the problems of continuous education. Pedagogical initiative includes the teacher's independent decision-making and activities aimed at improving existing educational practice. It also includes activities related to the development and application of new methods to achieve educational goals, promotion of new, prospective goals of education, creation of developments related to new pedagogical technologies, and the use of new pedagogical technologies in educational institutions.

Pedagogical initiative develops and becomes a standardized professional activity experience. Pedagogical initiative as a mechanism for the development of the personality of the future teacher and the implementation of his activity includes two components, developing the professional activity of the future teacher:

1. The content-based component of the initiative allows to determine the specific aspects of the personality of the future teacher.
2. The process-based component of pedagogical initiative is manifested in ensuring that all efforts of the future teacher are focused on the important aspects of the educational process.

In pedagogy, special attention is paid to the problem of renewal and implementation of one's own activities. The concept of renewal is related to the social activity of a person. It appears as an opportunity to ensure the social actions of a person. The level of innovation of a person's activity is determined by his attitude to the social environment. The concept of renewal is described in psychology as an opportunity for a person to develop his knowledge, behavioral style, and regular improvement, it is consistent with the concept of ensuring connection and is described as a phenomenon that means mental, emotional, kinetic actions and their transformation from a hidden potential state to improved actions. Alternatively, renewal is directly related to the concept of activity. This includes requirements, situations, setting goals, tasks arising from the situation, elimination of internal and external obstacles in the activity, creativity, cognitive activity, not being afraid of making mistakes. Most foreign experts used the concept of renewal in the humanistic, phenomenological (one of the directions of psychology) directions of personality theory.

The main goal of renewal is activation, striving for maturity. This approach forms the basis of the concept of K.Rogers. It is based on the model of self-awareness of the individual.

A.Maslow's concept of self-actualization states that proactive people can act outside of their personal interests. People who regularly improve their activities, abandoning uncertain actions, enter the ranks of concrete actions.

Most of the pedagogues did not describe the concepts of renewal and implementation of their activities separately. This concept is analyzed within the framework of the individual's self-development. The need to analyze personal activity requires updating and analyzing specific aspects of the concepts of personal activity. A person's activity is reflected in his creative activity. It finds its expression in the creative activity, volitional states, and communication of the specialist, and is evaluated as an active attitude of a person to the objective existence. A person's abilities arise as a result of his assimilation of social and cultural experience. A set of philosophical, pedagogical, psychological, sociological conditions allows to justify aspects of the concept of renewal and realization of one's own activity related to pedagogical initiative. Renewal as a process

of independent self-movement is carried out in connection with the internal and external capabilities of a person.

The main aspects of the implementation of pedagogical initiative are manifested in the following: the social and professional formation of the future teacher with external standards is reflected in the qualification requirements; such as initiative of future teachers as a subject of professional activity and its implementation.

The importance of forming pedagogical initiative in future teachers:

- pedagogical initiative, in which the future teacher's professional activity based on independent decision-making and the desire to improve the existing educational practice;

- movement of large-scale pedagogical initiatives aimed at implementation in specific pedagogical processes;

- pedagogical processes and socio-cultural mechanisms that are the basis for the teacher's self-development;

- Pedagogical processes that help the professional opportunities and abilities of the future teacher to be fully manifested;

- social pedagogical initiative, professional activity, creative ideas aimed at updating and improving the existing educational process, based on the individual's independent decision-making;

- activities aimed at updating the educational process based on large-scale pedagogical initiatives, as well as promoting specific pedagogical initiatives;

- competence of using social and cultural models in the process of acquiring professional knowledge and pedagogical approaches of future pedagogues;

- that future teachers fully demonstrate their professional abilities and capabilities in the process of pedagogical practice;

- it is assumed that the future teacher will be able to demonstrate the competence to rely on pedagogical standards and models, use diagnostic methods to study the educational process, etc.

In order to form these competencies, first of all, it is required to form educational initiative in future teachers as an important component of pedagogical initiative. In the framework of educational initiatives, future teachers should have the motivation to acquire professional knowledge and implement pedagogical activities. Systematic formation and development of such motives is one of the important tasks of the higher pedagogical education process.

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